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E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators: Celebrating Milestones and Future Directions

Work Package 5: Leading Innovation with Sarah De Coninck and E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

Unlocking the Future of Innovation

Work Package 5 develops methods to engage citizens and other stakeholders into research an innovation. The E³UDRES² alliance believes in a future international university where research, innovation and education departs from needs in the regions in which the universities are situated. To accomplish this, engagement of citizens and other stakeholders is crucial.

During the first year, work package 5 conducted Delphi rounds with experts in citizen science from all the E³UDRES² alliance institutions. In these Delphi rounds, experts gave feedback on engagement strategies proposed and suggested additional engagement strategies. Any issues with the interpretation of engagement strategies that existed, were resolved in a final voting webinar with experts. This resulted in a list of engagement strategies.

In a second step, these engagement strategies were divided into 8 categories of engagement skills for researchers, namely 1) design & plan, 2) communicate, 3) context, 4) networking, 5) teamwork, 6) train & educate, 7) incentives & motivation and 8) ethics. For each of these categories, engagement strategies were organized according to maturity level of the researchers exhibiting these skills. Inspiration was drawn from the EURAXES researcher profiles in order to define the different maturity levels.

In a next step, this maturity level will be tested out and further refined in a junior and a senior I-Living Lab.

Sarah De Coninck, WP5

One Laboratory, Multiple Interventions

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators stimulates international scientific dialog

In this edition of the Newsletter, Ricardo Nunes and Rui Morais (professor and Student from IPS) spoke with Luís Coelho, project coordinator of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators, outlined his profile and got to know his vision on the project and its results so far.

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators seeks to integrate science into society through international dialog. “How to reach citizens? How to motivate them and communicate effectively?” These are the central questions guiding the initiative.

Luís Coelho, who has a PhD degree in Mechanical Engineering, highlights the importance of international academic partnerships to overcome challenges and promote a broad, global academia. His professional career, from the study of fossil fuels to renewable sources, reflects this vision of energy transition and global collaboration.

The project, supported by the European Commission, has received excellent reviews, underlining its ability to involve citizens in research and increase the motivation of researchers. The aim is to create a unique, european institution that brings together forces and knowledge to solve local and global problems in a sustainable way.

“

**By chance, I am at IPS.
What is intended with this
European scope is that we
are no longer just an
institution in Portugal; we
are a European institution.**

Coelho, 2024

For more information visit
www.eudres.eu/entrenovators

“How do we reach the citizens? How do we motivate them? How do we communicate? How does a scientist, with their specific way of speaking, communicate in their language? How do we communicate with an ordinary citizen?” Luís Coelho presents the fundamental questions to highlight the complexity of the challenge at hand: “It's not easy.” Acknowledging the difficulty in aligning science with an informed, enlightened, and critical civil society, he anticipates an audacious operation for the partners that make up this academic alliance. This is why those in charge emphasize that the strength of partnerships is the key to success: “We need to work together, learn from each other, learn from what exists outside, and, in the end, I hope the result is very good.”

As broad as the vision traced in his career, which began with the study of fossil fuels, recognizing the need to find environmental alternatives to coal combustion. This led to the study of biomass and the essential and fundamental “transition to renewable energy sources.” All the planet's challenges were outlined in the researcher's path as he focused on studies of alternative combustion. And then? “After that, I also dedicated myself to solar thermal energy, geothermal energy, energy efficiency, particularly of buildings, various areas now more dedicated to the transition. And during all this time, I have worked on research projects at the European level, with consortia from various countries.”

The first two decades of the new millennium were decisive for taking the lead on European project focused on thermal energy storage coupled with solar and geothermal energy, for heating and cooling of the buildings. A flow of work and investment that culminated in the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project. With a broad vision, the institutional coordinator highlights this project in a dynamic, constructive, and innovative way, emphasizing that no researcher is an island, much less an isolated point: “Because I can easily move to another partner, easily use the other partner's laboratories, work with them, host students from other universities, send students to other universities. We probably already have common curricula, and therefore what I foresee is that we need a single institution, with this particularity of being in different countries.” Is the location where we do science relevant? That's the question we seek to answer.

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For the project coordinator, institutional alignment is key to optimizing a mechanism that, by bringing together various components, harmoniously contributes “to developing research and innovation within our universities, in cooperation with our regions, with stakeholders, with civil society, with citizens, in order to be a promoter of development for more sustainable and intelligent regions in the future.”

Halfway through its existence, the European Commission, the entity overseeing the project, positively recognized the work done: “It was a very good evaluation, an excellent evaluation. They considered that our project is producing very good results (smiles) and is being very well developed. For us, it was quite motivating,” highlights Luís Coelho. And for the formula to maintain its high standards, the action relies on seemingly simple and diverse ingredients, as, in the words of the leader, it is essential “to empower citizens to be involved in our research and, therefore, open up more to solve our citizens' problems and also increase the research conditions for our researchers to be more motivated.” If “for many years researchers worked very closed off, in their institutions and networks,” now the strategy will involve integrating science into society, opening doors for citizen participation, identifying where and how we can grow in this domain, which carries “many difficulties.” The alliance not only allows proximity with partner countries but also provides personal and collective growth, recognizing “where each institution is strongest, what areas it is strongest in, or what areas need help to increase their capacity,” it is thus collective work, the space is common, the agenda too. The stage is set for learning, among countries particularly different from each other, but united in forces and knowledge with a single goal. The project coordinator envisions the substantial work to be done with motivating expression, certain that much will remain to be done, although he acknowledges that the European alliance will bear many fruits.

For Luís Coelho, the project will provide the idea of “a single institution at the European level,” but which comprises a vast research community formed by different countries that use a broad list of jointly developed tools. “A common agenda on which we can have a base to guide us in what is important regarding research activities in our regions, our institutions, our alliance,” stresses the responsible. Ultimately, the ongoing dialogue among European partners seeks to answer the initial questions: How do we reach the citizens? How do we communicate? How do we communicate with an ordinary citizen?

Interview conducted and written by Ricardo Nunes and Rui Morais

JUNE 07th, 2024

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators international workshop at Polytechnic University of Setúbal

On June 7th, 2024, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project held a hybrid international workshop entitled “Open Science and Open Education”. The event, held at the Polytechnic University of Setúbal (IPS), was attended by several project partners, members of other international alliances and other guests. This conference reinforced the E³UDRES² alliance's commitment to promoting innovation and collaboration between European higher education institutions and to discussing and promoting open science and education practices.

The event began at 9:00 am with Luís Coelho, from IPS ESTSetúbal, presenting the objectives and achievements of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project. Karel Luyben, president of the European Open Science Cloud Association, emphasized the benefits of the European Open Science Cloud for promoting open science through accessible scientific data.

Silviu Vert from the Polytechnic University of Timisoara introduced digital tools that facilitate open science, enhancing access and collaboration. Professors Radu VasIU and Liviu Marsavina from the same university shared their experiences with open science and open access, discussing challenges and successes.

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E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators international workshop at Polytechnic University of Setúbal

Tassilo Pellegrini from St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences highlighted the importance of open license management for sharing and reusing scientific data. Joana Boavida-Portugal highlighted the ARNET Laboratory's data integration platform for collaborative science. The first part of the event concluded with a panel discussion moderated by Diana Andone, addressing key themes and participant questions.

In the second phase of the event, Sarah de Coninck addressed ethical considerations in open science and citizen science. Antónia Correia guided aligning with Horizon Europe's open science requirements. Sílvia Roda Couvaneiro discussed the impact of open pedagogies and emerging technologies on education. Diana Andone analyzed the opportunities and challenges of generative artificial intelligence in open education.

Jan-Hendrik Korber shared insights from the WATERLINE project on pan-European education. Michelle Perello presented the EXPER project, promoting innovation in remote regions. Irina Lungu and Marcello Costantini discussed the CONNECT platform from the BI4E project. A panel discussion moderated by Marta Frade followed. Pedro Manuel Antão introduced the InCITIES project, linking sustainable development with research hubs.

The event concluded with a final panel discussion moderated by Maria Catarina Paz, ending at 13:30 after a day of productive discussions on open science and education.

Luís Coelho, coordinator of the Ent-r-e-novators project, emphasized the significance of training courses on "Citizen Science" and "Open Science, Open Innovation, and Open Education." He noted that SWOT analyses were conducted at each member institution to optimize research resources and develop new support strategies.

Watch the full workshop on our YouTube channel [here!](#)

InCITIES Project: Pioneering Inclusive, Sustainable, and Resilient Urban Development

The InCITIES project, funded under the Horizon Europe program, aims to transform higher education institutions and their ecosystems by focusing on urban inclusion, sustainability, and resilience. Coordinated by ISCTE – University Institute of Lisbon, the project brings together five European universities—University of Zilina, University Gustave Eiffel, TH Koeln, and LAUREA—and 11 associated partners. This diverse consortium fosters cross-border cooperation and leverages a wide range of expertise to address the challenges facing Europe’s universities and cities.

A key component of InCITIES is its pilot Erasmus+ Blended Intensive Programme (BIP) on Sustainable Mobility Innovations. This course emphasizes a collaborative, student-centered learning approach. By integrating the learning-by-development model, the curriculum balances technical and interpersonal skills, ensuring students gain practical experience and knowledge necessary for urban planning and intervention.

Regular meetings and workshops are integral to the project’s progress. These collaborative sessions not only enhance institutional strategies but also foster a shared commitment to excellence in research.

In addition to in-person meetings, InCITIES hosts a series of online webinars called Scientific Cafés. These sessions are organized around thematic groups such as urban transition, nature in the city, energy, mobility, inclusion and health, digital transition, and sustainable cities. Researchers share their findings and methods, and foster collaborations for future projects, publications, and PhD co-supervisions.

By bringing together academic and practical expertise, the InCITIES project aims to make significant strides in creating cities that are inclusive, sustainable, and resilient.

For more information and updates, visit www.incities.eu and follow InCITIES on LinkedIn and X

Upcoming Citizen Science Workshop

2nd OCT 24

We continue our dedicated work on citizen science themes and are excited to announce the upcoming Citizen Science Workshop, which will take place on the 2nd of October at UCLL in Belgium.

This event will be held in a hybrid format, allowing both in-person and online participation. Stay tuned for more details, which will be shared soon on our website and social media channels.

E³UDRES² Upcoming events

The E³UDRES² Bootcamp 2024 offers students a unique opportunity to develop innovative solutions for regional healthcare challenges using AI. From July 1-5 in Limburg, Belgium, participants will work in small, interdisciplinary teams to co-create concepts that support the healthcare industry. This intensive five-day event covers various themes such as business, ethics, technology, health, and sustainability. Supported by mentors and external stakeholders, students will engage in a dynamic, creative environment, earning 3 ECTS upon completion. The Bootcamp aims to foster collaboration and enhance knowledge across diverse fields.

For more information, visit [E³UDRES² Bootcamp 2024](#)

1st - 5th JUL 24

E³UDRES² Bootcamp 2024: Innovating Healthcare with AI

14th – 18th OCT 24

IEC 2024: Building a Secure and Resilient Future through Digital Hygiene

The International Engagement Circus (IEC) 2024 edition, scheduled from October 14 to 18, revolves around the pivotal theme "Digital Hygiene: Building a Secure and Resilient Future." In a world where digital landscapes are fraught with risks for enterprises and institutions of all sizes, the concept of "Digital Hygiene" emerges as a crucial paradigm, since it emphasizes the importance of collectively creating protections through collaboration and the exchange of knowledge.

At the heart of IEC 2024 is the objective to identify problematic areas, gain new perspectives, drive industry improvements, and facilitate new connections. The event will delve into the influence of social media on mental health, examining how these platforms impact mental well-being and exploring strategies to mitigate their negative effects. Additionally, discussions will cover the critical issues of privacy and ethics, scrutinizing the ethical considerations surrounding data privacy and the responsibilities of organizations in safeguarding information. More details will be announced soon!

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